
Career Commitment and Work Performance among Senior High School Teachers

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Abstract

This study examined teachers' career commitment and work performance, it assessed their commitment to schools, students, teaching, profession, and finances, while work performance was evaluated using the Individual Plan for Career Growth and Development (IPCRF).

As to the respondents, the researcher used stratified random sampling with a proportional allocation of samples in choosing the respondents. The teachers demonstrated a strong commitment to their school, students, the teaching profession, and financial responsibilities. Their work performance, as assessed through the IPCRF, was exceptional. The findings indicated a significant relationship between the teachers' career commitment and their work performance, as determined by the Spearman-Rho Correlation Analysis. It was found that teachers' career commitment significantly influenced their work performance across four key result areas. Notably, commitment to the school and students emerged as strong predictors of the teachers' work performance.

In conclusion, the teachers' strong commitment to their careers greatly contributed to their exceptional work performance. This demonstrates that when teachers are highly dedicated in fulfilling their duties and responsibilities, their performance improves across all Key Result Areas in educating students. They foster positive social relationships among students and facilitate their success. Moreover, teachers exhibit a profound concern and passion for promoting both academic and social development by managing effective and efficient teaching strategies that enhance students' learning abilities. Furthermore, teachers' workload was the major issue that must be given attention.

1. Introduction

Commitment is indispensable to educators. Committed teachers have the excitement, passion, and desire to attain a high work performance. They show very important characteristics and enthusiasm for teaching as well as learning to enhance their competencies in doing their tasks.

These views concur to the statement of Serin (2017) that one of the most important elements in the development of a passion for teaching is the commitment and dedication of teachers to students and their learning. Thus, teachers need to be committed to their work to inspire their students and awaken their desire to learn.

Career-committed teachers are lifelong learners (Monsoer & Oci, 2015). They continue to learn from multiple sources of knowledge throughout their careers and have the opportunity to learn from practice by making mistakes, from students, and from other teachers and administrators. They must take steps to ensure not to marginalize or exclude any student due to their beliefs that differ from them. Teachers must motivate and guide students to engage in learning considering that not every child learn in the same way.

Relatively, there is a strong relationship between career commitment and work performance (Barnett, 2015). The correlation between them is significantly important to any organization to have a great positive response for employees' commitment and performance.

Teachers' commitment creates positive work performance. They keep abreast with the latest developments in education and never stop learning new methods as well as techniques and strategies (Cairo, 2019) for the students to continue learning in the modern world. It is education that makes better persons and more fulfilled individuals. The greatest career commitment of teachers if students under their care can truly open their minds and shape their future; thus, the DepEd mission (RA 9155) has been fully implemented.

Since teachers are important instruments in delivering quality education, they need to be equipped with pedagogical knowledge to perform best in their chosen career and be committed to their work as agents of change. However, Griffin (2016) mentioned that there are still adverse teachers' attitudes toward their teaching career, which may sum up to low career commitment that becomes a barrier to effective curriculum implementation (Blazr & Kraft, 2017), Hence, this study will be conducted to assess their career commitment and work performance as mentors because there has been no research conducted regarding the predictors of career commitment and work performance of the teachers in the region to improve their related work quality.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Teachers play an important role in educating the members of society through their work in school. As agent of change, they carry a heavy burden as they sail along in performing their task. Commitment and performance are their strongest weapon to sharpen the brain of their clientele, and through this, success in the educative process will be achieved. This study focused on teachers' career commitment and work performance. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the research questions indicated in Study 1 and Study 2 that follow:

1. What are the levels of teachers' career commitment in terms of commitment to school, students, teaching, and profession?
2. What is the level of teachers' work performance on KRAs based on their IPCRF?

3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' career commitment and teachers' work performance?
4. Is there a significant influence of career commitment on teachers' work performance?

1.2. Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Rational Choice Theory (Smith, 2022), which explains that individuals make decisions based on their goals and available alternatives to maximize personal benefits. Since resources and opportunities are limited, individuals calculate potential outcomes before making choices. This theory not only helps understand rational decision-making but also explains why some individuals make irrational choices (Ganti, 2021). It provides a structured approach to analyzing financial and professional decision-making, particularly how teachers allocate their time and resources to their careers and students.

Additionally, the study draws on the Financial Management Framework of Paceno and Laganhon (2022), which highlights four key financial practices—budgeting, spending, investing, and saving—as crucial elements in household financial stability. Poor financial management can affect a teacher's well-being, leading to financial stress that may impact their classroom performance. Teachers with strong financial literacy may exhibit higher job satisfaction and commitment to their students.

In the domain of career and job performance, Career Commitment Theory posits that an employee's level of dedication to their career directly influences job performance. Mansoer and Oli (2015) suggest that individuals with strong normative and affective commitment tend to perform better in their jobs. Employees who see their work as meaningful are more likely to invest in professional growth, leading to better classroom instruction and student engagement.

A significant aspect of career commitment in teaching is dedication to students' academic and personal development. Professional Dedication Theory highlights that teachers who are emotionally and intellectually committed to their profession are more likely to go beyond their required duties to ensure student success. Karagöz (2007) and Shukla (2014) describe

professional dedication as the emotional and cognitive connection of individuals form with their careers. A committed teacher sees their students' achievements as personal and professional fulfillment.

Studies suggest that teachers with strong commitment to their students Invest extra time in lesson planning, tutoring, and mentoring struggling students (Celep, 2014). Foster strong teacher-student relationships, which promote better academic performance and student motivation (Crosswell & Elliot, 2004). Adapt to student needs, modifying teaching strategies to accommodate different learning styles and abilities (Butucha, 2013). Serve as role models, inspiring students to develop discipline, responsibility, and a love for learning (Celep, 2014).

This study is also anchored in Performance Prediction Theory, which supports the idea that career commitment influences professional behavior and organizational success (Johnson, 2016). High commitment levels reduce job tardiness and absenteeism (Siu, 2015), while loyalty, experience, and knowledge contribute to sustained professional success (Yıldırım, 2019; Ataç, 2019).

Ultimately, this study seeks to examine the relationship between career commitment and teacher performance. Moreover, it focuses on how dedication to students influences work performance in selected schools within Cotabato Province's 2nd Congressional District.

2. Methods

This chapter contains the research design used, the locale of the study, respondents and sampling technique, instruments of the study used, data-gathering procedure, and statistical analysis of data.

2.1 Research Design

This research employed a mixed method design using the quantitative and qualitative methods of research in a concurrent method to improve the amount of information acquired as well as the credibility of the results. The structure as an item should be of adequate quality to

achieve validity and legitimacy (Johnson & Christensen, 2012). Quantitative research methods have specific properties that make them important for tackling a research topic.

Quantitative Method. This part of the study employed a descriptive-correlational approach. The researchers used descriptive design to determine SUCs' involvement in rural development and stakeholders' sustainable livelihood education. Correlational analysis was done to identify the variables' relationships and effects (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). Also, this research employed a quantitative approach, specifically a survey technique or survey research, to generate data from participants. Survey research collects data from a sample of people by asking them questions in the instrument (Check & Schutt, 2012). This kind of investigation examines some ways for selecting people, gathering information, and using various instrumentation procedures. An overview investigation may use quantitative examination processes, such as surveys with numerically evaluated items, subjective investigation systems, such as open-ended inquiries, or both.

2.2. Research Respondents

The study has a total of 155 respondents from the five (5) municipalities of the 2nd district of Cotabato, namely; Antipas, Arakan, Magpet, Makilala, and President Roxas. The respondents comprised Senior High School Teachers.

Table 1. Distribution of the respondents of the study.

Municipality	SHS Teachers
1. Antipas	17
2. Arakan	31
3. Makilala	47
4. Magpet	40
5. President Roxas	21
Total	155

2.3. Research Procedure

The researchers used stratified random sampling with the proportional allocation of samples. Proportional stratified random sampling involves taking random samples from stratified groups in proportion to the population. In disproportionate sampling, the strata are not proportional to their occurrence in the population (Thomas, 2023).

Stratified random sampling allow researchers to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied. Sampling involves statistical inference made using a subset of a population. Stratified random sampling is done by dividing the entire population into homogeneous groups called strata (V Parsons, Wiley StatsRef).

2.4. Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study was an adopted questionnaire from Majd Mrayyon, PhD and Ibrahim Al-Fouri, PhD, in their research Nurses Commitment and Job Performance; Differences between intensive care units and Wards. This questionnaire was modified and restructured fitted to evaluate teachers' commitment.

This instrument used in the investigation has two parts. Part A has 13 items which comprises four labels; Commitment to School, Commitment to Students, Commitment to Teaching, and Commitment to Profession. Part B was all about the demographic characteristics of the respondents, and it included five items. The teaching performance was measured using the DepEd COT-RPMS which is secondary data. It consists of nine items with a number indicator of 1,2,3,4, and 5. The indicators measure the teachers' performance during classroom observation on an individual basis, regardless of each relationship to other indicators.

Part A reflected the level of teachers' career commitment on different commitment areas such as commitment to school, student commitment, teaching, and profession.

Table 2a. Likert Scale on the Levels of Teachers' Career Commitment

Level	Range	Description	Descriptive Interpretation	Percentage
5	4.21-5.00	Highly Committed	The item described is always observed or the condition is very extensive.	81%-100%
4	3.41-4.20	Committed	The item described is observed or the condition is moderately extensive.	61%-80%
3	2.61-3.40	Moderately Committed	The item described is sometime observed or the condition is met.	41%-60%
2	1.81-2.60	Less Committed	The item described is slightly observed or the condition is limited.	21%-40%
1	1.00-1.80	Not Committed	The item described is not observed.	1%-20%

Part B reflected the level or the adjectival rating equivalences on the teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF).

Table 2b. IPCRF Adjectival Rating Equivalences

Level	Range	Description	Descriptive Interpretation	Percentage
5	4.500-5.000	Outstanding	The item described is always observed or the condition is very extensive.	81% - 100%
4	3.500-4.499	Very Satisfactory	The item described is observed or the condition is moderately extensive.	61% - 80%
3	2.500-3.499	Satisfactory	The item described is sometime observed or the condition is met.	41% - 60%
2	1.500-2.499	Unsatisfactory	The item described is slightly observed or the condition is limited	21% - 40%
1	Below 1.499	Poor	The item described is not observed.	1% - 20%

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were followed during the conduct of the study:

Validation. The researchers prepared the survey questionnaires that were used in this study and submitted it to the experts in the field for validation.

Permission. After the validation of the research instruments, a letter of approval to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School of Cotabato Foundation College of Science and Technology were obtained noted by the adviser. Upon approval, the researchers used the forms of data collection as recommended.

2.6. Data Analysis

Data and Statistical Analysis

Statistical tools used in processing the collected data. Statements of career commitment and work performance among high school teachers were tabulated using weighted mean (Swinscow & Campbell, 2003). Meanwhile, the relationship was processed using Spearman Rho's Correlation Coefficient (Hinkle, Wiersma, & Jurs, 2003) while the significant influence was measured using Multiple Linear Regression (Fahrmeir, Kneib, & Lang, 2009).

Data entry were then undertaken. The quantitative data obtained from questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics. This involved the use of weighted mean. Descriptive statistical techniques reduce data to manageable proportions by summarizing them and they also described various characteristics of the data under study.

The items in career commitment questionnaire were organized into four subscales namely: Commitment to School, Commitment to Students, Commitment to Teaching, and Commitment to Profession. The individual items that were in each subscale.

3. Results

The teachers were found to be highly committed to the school, students, teaching, profession, and their financial responsibilities. Additionally, the teachers' work performance based on their IPCRF is outstanding. Particularly, for content knowledge and pedagogy. They manifested mastery of content knowledge of subjects within and across curriculum teaching areas and the right choice of teaching strategies that enhance learners' achievements.

They exceptionally managed classroom structure to engage learners individually or in groups. They consider a favorable climate for their educational institutions, teaching activities, teaching profession, and workgroup colleagues. Moreover, the teachers manifest outstanding work performance in planning, managing, and implementing developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes. They strive to meet the curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts including the use of instructional materials.

The teachers also have outstanding performance in designing assessment tools (KRA 4) aimed at measuring student learning and fair reporting. They also designed, selected, organized, and used diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements. Further findings show that in crafting assessment tools, the teachers prefer to maximize their performances in planning and conceptualizing learning contents and activities with the prescribed basic education curriculum to align their plans in preparing test questions be it formative or summative assessment tools. Remarkably, the teachers attended various related training and seminars that contributed to the teaching-learning process very satisfactorily.

Findings revealed a significant relationship between the teachers' career commitment and work performance using the Spearman-Rho Correlation Analysis. There was a highly significant relationship between teachers' career commitment and all KRA performance of teachers but a low correlation between teachers' commitment to school and all factors used to measure their work performance.

On the fourth research problem, findings showed a significant influence of teachers' career commitment on their work performance in the four (4) key result areas as to teachers' work performance. This includes content knowledge and pedagogy (KRA 1), curriculum planning (KRA 3), assessment and reporting (KRA 4), and attendance in training and seminars (KRA 5).

4. Recommendation

Based on the preceding findings and conclusions, this study recommends the following as a basis for program enhancement.

1. The teachers consider maintaining their career commitment to increase their sense of obligation toward the fulfillment of the school goals and quality education for the new generation.
2. School heads may consider recognizing teachers with outstanding performance based on the KRAs.
3. School heads may schedule in-school enhancement activities such as demonstration teaching and mentoring to enhance instructional practices emphasizing teaching methods, strategies, and techniques in delivering a subject matter and leading learners to understand and master content emphasizing mastery and motivation of learners.
4. School heads may also consider the schedule of teachers working for advanced degree programs in their line of specialization to inspire them to continue their studies.
5. The researchers encourages incoming researchers to replicate this study to continuously monitor and measure the degree of sustaining high commitment and quality work performance of teachers.
6. Schools may consider reviewing the memorandums specifying teachers' workload.

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